

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B403
Date: 22/09/08
Take Off: 07:48:00
Landing: 12:50:07
Flight Time 5h 02m 07s

Campaign: VACAR

Operating Area: SW Approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Chawn Harlow	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	
8	ARIES / Wet Neph / PSAP	Stuart Newman	Met Office	
9	ARIES	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / SHIMS	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	CVI / FWVS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
12	TAFTS	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	
13	MARSS/DEIMOS / Mission Scientist 2	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B403
 Date: 22nd September 2008
 Project: VACAR
 Location: SW Approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
054127		Start-Up	0.00 kft	305	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
073617		Start-Up	0.00 kft	003	engine start
074219		event	0.00 kft	009	start taxi
074800		T/O	0.00 kft	282	Cranfield
075214		event	7.2 kft	275	Nevzorov, JW zero
075541		event	10.0 kft	055	Nevzorov, JW zero
081932		event	20.0 kft	255	Nevzorov, JW zero
082608		event	20.0 kft	255	JW zero
082618	085109	Profile 1.1	20.0 - 0.05 kft	255	
082747		event	18.7 kft	267	extend BBR
084051		event	4.4 kft	261	JW zero
084613		event	1.6 kft	261	retract BBR
085228	090231	Run 1.1	0.10 kft	178	Heimann cal
090403	090823	Profile 2.1	0.05 - 3.5 kft	354	
090512		event	0.76 kft	344	bbr extend
090837	091622	Profile 3.1	3.6 - 0.05 kft	354	
091622	092214	Profile 4.1	0.05 - 3.6 kft	172	
092214	093216	Profile 5.1	3.6 - 0.05 kft	178	
093216	094643	Profile 6.1	0.05 - 7.0 kft	012	
093329		event	0.36 kft	008	Nevzorov, JW zero
094743		event	7.0 kft	279	bbr retract
094834	095833	Run 2.1	7.0 kft	002	
095004		event	7.0 kft	008	Nevzorov, JW zero
095843	103707	Profile 7.1	7.0 - 34.0 kft	006	
103718	104406	Run 3.1	34.0 kft	195	
104003		Sonde 1	34.0 kft	195	
104407	105355	Run 3.2	34.0 kft	352	contrailing at FL340
104505		Sonde 2	34.0 kft	354	
105624	110621	Run 3.3	34.1 - 33.0 kft	192	
105634		Sonde 3	34.1 kft	195	
105930		event	33.7 kft	196	Nevzorov, JW zero
110122		Sonde 4	33.0 kft	195	
110646	111258	Profile 8.1	33.0 - 27.1 kft	178	
111314	111927	Profile 9.1	27.0 - 30.0 kft	353	
112150	112355	Profile 9.1	30.0 - 31.0 kft	167	
112422	113259	Profile 10.1	31.0 - 6.8 kft	167	
113313	114405	Profile 10.1	6.6 - 0.05 kft	059	500 fpm
114319		event	-.02 kft	050	Nevzorov, JW zero

125007	Land	0.00 kft	214
125335	Shutdown	0.00 kft	306 at Cranfield

B403 Track 22-SEP-08

**VACAR -Variational Assimilation of Cloud Affected Radiances.
Cirrus with stratocumulus or broken cumulus below and IASI overpass at 1045Z**

Aim

To gather a data set that can be used to test the 1d-var assimilation of cloud affected ARIES and/or IASI spectra.

Measurement Requirement

1. Profiles of temperature, water vapour and ozone,
2. Measure of the sea surface temperature and emissivity and surface wind speed
3. Measurements of the physical position of the clouds e.g. cloud top and base altitude and temperature
4. Measurements of the cloud microphysical properties – vertical structure and horizontal variability
5. Measurements of ARIES, SWS and MARSS spectra looking down through clouds and upwards above clouds.
6. Dropsondes through the atmosphere during high level runs above clouds.
7. Ideally coincident with IASI satellite overpass during high level runs.

Sortie structure

1. Take off and transit to area profiling to arrive at 50ft (45 mins)
2. Straight and level run at 100ft over fixed ground positions oriented to cross sub-satellite track diagonally if near nadir or at angle ~30deg off satellite track for runs further away from sub satellite track (10 mins, 55 total)
3. Profile to level above cloud tops (10 mins, 65 total)
4. **If Stratocumulus then:** A series of saw tooth profiles crossing the cloud top boundary from 1000ft above cloud to 1000ft below cloud tops (60 mins) **If broken cumulus then:** A series of saw tooth profiles from 1000ft above cloud tops to 1000ft below cloud base – adjust some profiles to ensure that some pass through cloud and others through the breaks (60 mins, 140 total)
5. Straight and level run above boundary layer cloud (10 mins, 135 total)
6. Profile to level safely above cirrus clouds (30 mins, 165 total)
7. Two straight and level runs above cirrus clouds, one to be coincident with IASI overpass at **1045Z**, launch two sondes on each run, run duration 10 mins (25 mins, 190 total)
8. Series of saw tooth profiles through the cirrus from above cloud to 1000ft below cloud (60 mins, 250 total)
9. Profile to lowest permitted altitude stepping to remain in same geographic area (30 mins, 280 total)
10. Transit back to Cranfield (45 mins, 325 total)

B403 – Flight Debrief
Campaign: VACAR
Mission Scientist: Chawn Harlow

Decision for go/no-go were complicated by slow MO computing facilities at FAAM. Prior to flight both areas A and C were holding promise for a mixed SCu/Ci VACAR sortie. Decision for area A were based on easier low level operation in SW Approaches. Models and satellite images were showing good SCu/Cu in NW portions of area A (south of Irish FIR) with some Ci forecast to arrive during the early part of the sortie.

The conditions for this VACAR sortie were slightly marginal. However, discussions with the PI on the project have confirmed that this is likely to be a good case. There was a fairly good deck of broken Cu between 1000' and 7000', but the Ci overhead was fairly variable in space and time with the overall cover increasing between the low level and high level work. During low level work the Ci appeared to be constrained to the N^{ern} half of the SLR at 7000'. The instruments worked beyond expectations throughout with several profiles through the low level cloud layer and three through the Ci. The aircraft was in position in the high level run during the 1045Z IASI overpass. Profiles were at 500 fpm in the boundary layer and 1000 fpm above except in the last descending profile. During this latter profile from FL330 to 50', the rate of descent was increased during the cloud-free portion down to the top of the boundary layer due to fuel constraints.

After transiting to the operating area, a profile descent was carried out from FL200 to 50' above the sea. A straight and level run (SLR) was carried out at 100' above the sea surface to sample sea surface temperature and emissivity as well as the low level wind conditions. Broken Cu were observed above on the whole of this run. A profile was then carried out to 4000' during which cloud bases and tops were at approximately 1000' and 3200' asl, respectively. Two profiles were performed from 1000' above cloud top to 50' and back up again. The final of the saw-tooth profiles was terminated at 7000' as the cloud appeared to have grown during the saw-teeth. An SLR was carried out at 7000' followed by a profile up to FL 340 during which thin Ci was observed between FL 280 and FL 310. two SLR's were then performed at FL340 coincident with the satellite overpass and launching two sondes on each. A saw-tooth profile was then carried out from FL 340 to FL 270 and back up again. One final deep profile was then carried out to 50' with the above mentioned steep descent before transiting back to Cranfield.

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.403**... Date 22/9/08... Name Chawa Harlow Page 1 of 4...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
074854	T/O				Take off Cranfield
					Instrument Status Check:
					ARIES - OK
					SWS - OK
					MARSS - OK
					Cloud Phys - OK
					CVI - OK Hygro bad
					AVAPS - Not on yet
					TAFTS - OK!
					Core - OK GIN hiccup at start
082618	P1.1	FL200			Start
084000					Broken Cu Below
					Alt Cut above
085109	P1.1	100'			End
085228	R1	100'			Alt Cu clearing above
					Broken ↳ SCu ahead
0854ish					" overhead
					Ch.1 PCASP noisy
					FFSSSP "
					White Horses below
090231	R1				
090403	P2.1				Broken Cu whole run
					1000' cloud Base
					~3200' cloud tops

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.403** Date 22/9/08 Name C. Harbow Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
090823	P3.1	4000'			Start P3.1/End P2.1
					P3.1 Cloud free
					Turn to avoid cloud +
					avoid Irish airspace
					Just clipped bottom of
					cloud
091622	P3.1	50'			End ↓
"	P3.1 P4.1				Start ↑ - Cloudy profile
092214	P5.1	3750'			Start ↓
					Cloud Phys happy
093216	P6.1	50'			Start ↑
					Bound layer top ~6000ft
094643	P6.1	7000'			End
094834	R2.1	7000'			Start Mostly Clear above
					thin wispy Ci on N end
095400					Ci Above
					Aerosol plume seen in PCASP
					concentration increased on N end
					of run
095843	R2.1				End
"	P7.1	7000'			Start
1023 ish		FL280			Ci Base shows up on CPhys
103707	P7.1/R3.1	FL340			End/Start Run not SLR
104003	S1	FL340			Sonde 1 - Turn onto recip.
104407	R3.2	"			Start

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.403** Date **22/9/08** Name **C. Harlow** Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
104505	S2	FL340			Sonde 2
		"			Contraailing
1052 ish					Sonde 1 splash down
105355	R3.2	FL340			End
105624	R3.3	"			Start
105634	S3	"			Sonde 3
1057					Sonde 2 in water
110122	S4	FL340			
1059		FL340			Divert to lower level FL330
1101		FL330			Resume
					F332 - Contraailing Stopped
					S1, 2+4 Good
					S3 GPS problem to FL180
100621	R3.3				End
110646	P8.1	FL330			Start ↓
					Contraailing intermit.
1109					Sonde 3 in water
111258	P8.1				End
111314	P9.1				Start ↑ - Sonde 4 in water
					Ci looking thicker from above
111927	P9.1				Interrupt
112150	P9.1				Resume
112355	P9.1	FL330			End
112422	P10.1	FL330			Start

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B403

Date:22/09/08 Operator:PDR DRS time: DAU1 time: DAU2 time: DAU3 time: AUX1 time: AUX2 time: Page 1 of 1
 Pcasv vref 7.5, flow 0.82, ffssp vref 3.3, 2dc end elements 1.3,1.4

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/c	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
																Not running 2dp	
																Start profile 1.1	
08:33:30	200																
08:38:00	300															Entered boundary layer at ~fl 70	
08:43:00	1500															Fl 30	
08:45:00	2000															Fl 23	
08:45:45	1000					10										Fl 16 passed through cloud	
08:47:50	600															Fl 10	
08:49:00																Possible noise spikes seen on pcasp ch1 correlating with sapikes in ffssp strobe counts	
08:51:10	250															50 ft end profile 1.1	
																Start run 1.1	
08:55:00	300																
08:59:00	500																
09:02:30	1200															End run 1.1	
																Start Profile 2.1	
09:06:00	1000															Fl 15 some cloud penetrated	
09:08:00	600															Fl 30	
																End profile 2.1 start profile 3.1	
09:14:30	650															Fl 5 some cloud penetration during descent conc 10/L seen on 2dc	
09:16:20	700															End profile 3.1 start profile 4.1 50 ft	
09:22:10	1000															End profile 4.1 start profile 5.1	
09:28:05	1400		434													Fl 10	
09:32:10	500		533													50 ft end profile 5.1 start profile 6.1	
09:38:40	1000		539													Fl 30	
09:43:00	500		539													Fl 50	
09:47:00	70		539													Fl70 exit boundary layer end profile 6.1 start run 2.1	
09:56:00	200		540														
09:58:30	250		541													End run 2.1 start profile 7.1	
09:05:00	10		542													Initial steep decrease to ~50 counts/cc on pcasp at start of ascent followed by gradual decrease to ~10 counts/cc	
10:24:00	10		546			50										One spike on 2dc to 250 counts/L	
10:37:00																Noise on pcasp ch1 caused by cold conditions at high alt	
10:09:30						50											
11:14:10						150										Fl 275 2 cloud layers seen by 2dc	
11:18:10			588			200										Fl295	
1133:00	500		619													Entered boundary layer	
11:37:10	1000		622													Fl 40	
11:39:00	1500		624													Fl30	
11:44:05	800		635													50 ft	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B403 **T/O:** 07:48:00
Date of flight: 22/09/08 **Land:** 12:50:07

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B403
Date of Flight: 22/09/08

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	11496 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 138924
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 39933 Blocks written = 39933 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 074500 End = 125500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Occasional noise on 2dc but mostly good images. Mainly ice. No 2dp Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 074500 End =125500 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions 4 pages 2dc

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = b403_tas</p> <p>Start = 074500 End = 125500</p> <p>Time data processed to = 124520 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 273</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = b403_tas Y = (X+1) = b403_tas_2d</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B403
Date of Flight: 22/09/08

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 0.82
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = b403_tas_2d Y = X+1 =_tas_2d_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Y Use flight_plot to check. Noise PCASP 0950-1200?

B403CVI.txt

9/22/08 8:26:58 AM Start of profile descent
9/22/08 8:33:28 AM Into SC5
9/22/08 8:34:06 AM And out again
9/22/08 8:37:48 AM Back in sc5
9/22/08 8:41:09 AM sc5 to thin/bkn coming out of cvi mode
9/22/08 8:45:42 AM back into small cul
9/22/08 8:47:57 AM below cloud
9/22/08 8:51:19 AM end of profile descent
9/22/08 8:52:30 AM start of run 1
9/22/08 9:02:39 AM end of run 1
9/22/08 9:04:04 AM start of profile 2
9/22/08 9:05:08 AM into cul
9/22/08 9:08:45 AM profile descent
9/22/08 9:08:54 AM profile descent 3.1
9/22/08 9:09:34 AM Re-entering sct cul
9/22/08 9:10:11 AM per mission sci - now cloud free so back out of cvi mode
9/22/08 9:16:42 AM end of profile 3.1 and start of profile 4.1
9/22/08 9:22:28 AM end of profile 4.1 start of profile 5.1
9/22/08 9:32:29 AM end of profile 5.1 start of 6.1
9/22/08 9:46:51 AM end of profile climb
9/22/08 9:48:42 AM start of slf run 2.1
9/22/08 9:58:39 AM end of run
9/22/08 9:58:51 AM start of profile climb
9/22/08 10:37:22 AM end of profile climb and start of run
9/22/08 10:38:26 AM end of profile climb and start of run
9/22/08 10:44:15 AM start of run 3.2
9/22/08 10:45:05 AM iasi overpass (dropsonde 2)
9/22/08 10:47:48 AM spike on hygrometer appears to be coincident with sonde launch.
Possibly detaching small pressure change!?
9/22/08 10:53:56 AM end of run
9/22/08 10:56:24 AM start of run 3.3
9/22/08 10:57:20 AM Hygro spike occurred 1 min before dropsonde - ruining my theory
almost instantly
9/22/08 11:00:28 AM Spike occurred as dropmaster confirmed "sonde ready".....
9/22/08 11:06:24 AM end of run
9/22/08 11:06:54 AM start of profile descent
9/22/08 11:10:35 AM Ok hygro spikes appear to be random
9/22/08 11:13:23 AM end of profile descent and start of profile climb from fl270
9/22/08 11:19:38 AM end of profile climb at fl300
9/22/08 11:22:09 AM profile climb resumed to fl310
9/22/08 11:24:22 AM end of profile 9.1 at fl310
9/22/08 11:24:35 AM start of profile descent 10.1
9/22/08 11:44:25 AM end of profile - end of science

ARIES flight log

Flight: B403

page 1 of 2

Date: 22/9/08

Operator(s): S. NEWMAN / D. O'SULLIVAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VACAR / SW Approaches

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
063121	---	1x30 1x	C	C	71	33	On pan pre-flight
063158	---	1x30	H	C	71	32	
063240	---	120x1	N	C	71	32	
063353	---	1x30	C	C	71	32	
063417	---	1x30	H	C	71	31	
063510	---	120x1	Z	O	71	32	
063621	---	1x30	C	O	71	32	
063643	---	1x30	H	O	71	31	
064051	---	9.N30s	-	O	71	30	064540 aborted Calibrated display: wrong e.g. HBB 71°C displays as 2.54 K
065409	-	6.Z30s	-	O	71	31	065747 abort Display of raw spectra also in error? 2nd part BB at 23.4/.6°C (?)
07148	TAKE-OFF						
075834	In transit	10.NZ30s	-	O	71	32	2.483 K CBB } script hung!
080140	"	"	-	O	70	31	2.536 K HBB } from display! Sc below, clear above 081353 abort, still Sc below clear above
085131	100ft	10.NZ30s	-	O	71	30	Cal in turn before run; CuSc above 090233 abort
094716	7000ft	10.NZ30s	-	O	71	31	Above BL cloud (broken) First few nadir spectra in turn Looks quite clear above, cloud+haze below 0955 under cirrus now? patchy 095837 abort Radiance -2.995 -ve values display -3

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	22/09/08	Flight	B403	log pages	3
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	VACAR			
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on			at time	05:58			
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	17.5°C	Ch	17.4°C	Ch18	16.8°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on			at time	05:59			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289.3	Cold	286.8			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	06:00			
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual		X

Deimos

Deimos Orientation (Nadir or Zenith)							Z
Close all Deimos circuit breakers							X
Turn on Deimos CPU							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Start Deimos Software			at time	06:00			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289.9	Cold	288.1			
Target heating							X
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual		X
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	07:24			
Brightness temps 'sensible'							X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.9	Cold	296.73		
	Deimos:	Hot	344.5	Cold	287.8		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	53.5	15.6	54.7	14.1			
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20		
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)		
	39.12	33.93	37.88	41.59	43.15		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again						at time	

Flight #	B403	Date	22/09/08	Operator(s)	Pollard	log page	3	of	3
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>				Sys		

Data Processing Log		Initials	Date
Flight data copied from MARSS/Deimos PC flash disk to Martian C:\Bxxx\			
Check disc space on flash disk (need >~10 MB free)			
Copy* Martian logged data from to C:\Bxxx\			
Wave processing run and BT files generated			
DQM file generated and uploaded			
NetCDF file generated and uploaded			
C:\Bxxx\ copied to USB drive or CD			
Data processing issues/notes:			

Flight:

B403

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Fax machine:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom C:
 Satcom H:
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP (fuselage):
 CDP (Canister):
 CIP 100:
 CIP 25:
 CPI:
 CVI:
 SID1:
 SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC 3025 (AMS):
 INC:
 VACC:
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 SP2:
 UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR:
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B403

Date: 22/09/08

Instruments

1. GIN failed to initialise correctly, navigating at a position 84N. Turned off/on (twice) then ok. CPC – could not get AIM software to run, i.e. would not go past Error messages “The parameter is not correct” and AIM MFC Application Error. Pre-flight and in flight
2. Mission Scientist laptop – mouse not working correctly
3. Noise on PCASP and FSSP
4. 2DP not run
5. SWS module dropped out twice
6. ARIES display problem
7. FWVS not working in auto mode

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

nil

MPDS

Tested during flight - FAAM

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 22/09/08

Flight No: B 403

Pre-Flighter: MS

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	RFC out of focus
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	Status 4088 (norm 4089)
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom C	Checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	Use laptop
*		ecN	Water x 2 bottles	low but cant remove ids as so tight
*		CPC	Aim software hangs.	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	Debris inside clear dome
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs	Checked & Cleaned	Signed
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX	applied	
46	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B403:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as Stuart Newman was operating Wet Neph and not trained on PSAP
SHIMS	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
Wet Neph	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
CPI log	CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
Dry Neph	operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	09 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following video recordings in avi format should be available at the BADC :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_075424_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_085424_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_095424_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_105424_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_115424_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_075415_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_085415_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_095415_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_105415_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_115415_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_075410_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_085410_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_095410_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_105410_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_115410_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_075419_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_085419_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_095419_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_105419_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080922_r0_b403_115419_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.